

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HUNDISSA****FIRST NAME: ENDRIS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Logics in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Quotation and Paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 6-10)
3. Importance of Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
5. CMS special uses of Italics and Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 47-49)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 59-61)

GUIDANCE IN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one revised by Pr. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019) is focused on providing compressive guidance in academic essay writing. The coursepack is suitably designed for students at both master's and doctoral levels. The coursepack elaborates on main essay writing procedures with clear cut rules of thumbs, plagiarism, literature review, general citation guidance, and Chicago Manual Style (CMS) that is specifically required by this course. It also briefly highlights the primary variations between American and British English in academic essay writing and how to use the Latin abbreviations and expressions carefully.

In an academic essay, researchers strive to build new knowledge on the existing ones. Therefore, skimming into all the relevant and reliable sources on time has paramount significance. The coursepack states, "The feature of academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital in essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question" (EUCLID 2019, 2).

2) THE LOGICS IN ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack deals with academic essay writing basics to advance knowledge on a particular area of study. I realized that an academic essay is a rational communication based on logical justifications to build knowledge. It is a compelling way of communication that differs from the ordinary knowledge transfer in that the former is reason driven and justifies the rations with evidence. Academic essay convinces the readers easily because it enriched with relevant examples, solidifying evidence, information from pre-built scientific sources (EUCLID 2019, 1).

The coursepack triggered my long-time memory in which one of my students argued that “traditionally inherited knowledge and experience are the best sources of knowledge than scientific research approach.” The student tried to justify his position saying, “inherited and knowledge through experience is deep-rooted, generational, widely accepted, less costly and equally accessible.” However, most of the inherited knowledge is not reasonably justifiable and lacks evidential proves. For example, people believed the sun revolves around the earth but scientifically proved that vice versa is true lately. On the contrary, an academic essay requires as many sources as possible and precise pieces of evidence that can be verified by the readers to trust the reliability of the researcher (EUCLID 2019, 2).

I have also found out that an academic essay is as good as its presentation. It is digging into the sources and collecting relevant and reliable data, and writing the essay following standardized procedures is equally important in its acceptance with the readers. How the researcher strives to answer the question, the kind of evidence and examples used to elaborate the answer, and how the argumentation is built coherently would enhance the trust readers bestowed on the researcher (EUCLID 2019, 3).

3) ACADEMIC OFFENSES IN ESSAY WRITING

The second chapter of the Coursepack stirs the emotion I had while evaluating my undergraduate students' academic papers several years ago. Some of them used to cut and paste from the sources with minor editions that amounts plagiarism (EUCLID 2020, 3). Furthermore, most of them did not acknowledge the sources of the ideas and information to their academic papers unless they directly quote word for word. Therefore, many of us misunderstand citation as buying the authors of our sources' words and sentences than ideas and information, which is more critical in my view. However, it is indicated in the coursepack that paraphrased sources deserve equal acknowledgment of those quoted (EUCLID 2019, 8). Moreover, I realized that citing paraphrased sources is essential in avoiding plagiarism and giving our readers the chance to read the sources of essential ideas and information in our essay.

I have found out that plagiarism is using the authors' ideas and information without giving them recognitions and misquoting and misinterpreting their ideas to mislead the

readers (EUCLID 2019, 8). Therefore, I would recommend to the students taking this course, especially beginners in research, to read and understand this chapter of the coursepack to overcome the fear of plagiarism and properly use in-text citations and referencing.

4) THE IMPORTANCE OF STYLE GUID

Chapter six of the coursepack briefly summarizes the importance of the style guide. In my understanding, the style guide is conformity to specific standards set by a group of people, institutions, or nations to keep coherence and consistency in performance. For example, EUCLID usually advises students to use the Chicago style of citation and referencing, unless otherwise specified, and American English for Return Paper (RP), Major paper (MP), and Quiz preparation (EUCLID 2019, 24). During the globalization era, where daily communications transgress boundaries, having a detailed style guide would ease effective formal communication between institutions and businesses in different parts of the world. It also universalizes the ethical use of standard tools such as information technology to enhance their roles in changing lives positively and overcome the side effects.

5) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

At the begging of chapter eight (8) of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Period (1) coursepack, Dr. Abel Scribe compiled a crib sheet that illustrates the elements in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). He categorized them into three subheadings: "Chicago style and usage; Chicago page formatting, and Chicago end and footnotes" (EUCLID 2019, 44). I have found the arrangement helpful because researchers can quickly identify what is required to use CMS on a single page, and professors can also use it as a page manual to evaluate their students' essay papers. Furthermore, I came to know that CMS is used in formatting research papers and book documentation. For research papers, CMS uses "Turabian Style," which was first compiled by Kate Turabian at the University of Chicago and edited by different scholars several times (EUCLID 2019, 44). Sources I read indicate that many universities and research institutions have been preferably using CMS as guidance for years, because of its clarity, consistency, and less complexity. EUCLID also recommend Turabian author-date citation style for its students unless otherwise specified.

Proper citation is as essential as having reliable and relevant data because readers look for evidence to trust research papers and trust the evidence from credible sources. Based on the area of their study, researchers can use one of the two Turabian citation styles. For example, Turabian recommends note-bibliography style for those researching in humanity and specific social science fields, and author-date citation style for researchers in natural and social science areas (Turiabian 2008, 25). The same way organ system operates in coordination, CMS also comprises coordinated elements, from the main heading on the first page to the list of References on the last page, to make academic writings functional. Therefore, the citations and references combined with all the remaining

elements under the three subheadings make the CMS system operational. Although a system cannot operate well with a malfunction of one of its parts, I would like to highlight some CMS elements with new insights and think it would benefit other students taking this course.

a) Headings and Capitalization

Before I read CMS, I was confused about using capitalization in the headers of academic essays. I usually use heading and sentence capitalizations with bolding, italics, and numbering as needed for headers, including the major headers. Furthermore, I seldomly use the headings board on my computer but manually assign headings to my academic writings. The three CMS headings and capitalization styles would clarify the fogs students might have on essay headings and capitalization issues. Accordingly, the manual requires full capitalization of every word's character in major headings; capitalization of the first and last words and associated nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and subordinating conjunctions.

Furthermore, the sentence cap capitalizes the first word of a title, the first word after a colon, and pronouns (EUCLID 2019, 45). I have clarified the fog surrounding me regarding whether to capitalize or not the articles, conjunctions, prepositions, and infinitive in headings. Now it is clear that students are not required to capitalize on them in the headers.

b) Italics

In addition to serving commonly known purposes, the coursepack illustrates the exceptional uses of italics in an academic essay in detail. For example, I realized a writer could use italics to alert the readers about anything irony and emphasized phrases or words in the text (EUCLID 2019, 48). One of the weakest sides of written language is the lack of conveying emotional feelings and sign communications. For example, readers cannot get data sources' personal feelings in interviews and focus group discussions, and the researcher could not convey all of those emotions through the research report.

c) Quotation Marks

Researchers use quotations to take the exact words or phrases of sources referenced for the academic paper; to elicit vital evidence that can support the thesis answer. In a few incidents, while reading books and research papers, I encountered several words and phrases in quotation marks for non-quote purposes and wondered about their purpose. However, after reading this coursepack, I realized that quotations could also be used in exceptional circumstances other than source quotes. One instance is that when the researcher encounters expressions with unique sense or deliberately misused words in the sources and wants to inform the readers about them in the research paper. Moreover, as per the CMS guide, researchers can faithfully indicate a language line's fault, including inappropriate words in the sources by putting them in the quotations (EUCLID 2019, 48).

6) THE INVISIBLE INTERNATIONAL LANGUAGE

I asked my son what time he was going to the soccer club yesterday. He replied that "you have to drop me at 2:30 PM, and our game vs team B will start at 3:00 PM." What can people recall from his response? Latin by *de facto* is an invisible international language. It is used in every part of the world; however, people rarely recognize even using the language. As a result, if you ask the origin of Latin terms they use in daily communication, they probably do not know or tell you it is English. Every profession uses Latin terms, especially the health and medical sectors use it wildly, and therefore, professionals in that sector would better understand how to use and the exact meanings of those terms. Therefore, the ACA-401 coursepack guides students not to use Latin Abbreviations and expressions in the body of formal essays to avoid readers misunderstanding. The coursepack illustrated the Latin expressions and abbreviations with their English translations to avoid confusion when used with English words in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 56-61).

7) CONCLUSION

It is good to start the long journey of a doctoral degree with the basics of essay writing, whose impacts last as far as somebody is a student and even beyond. I have found the topics in the coursepack timely, fruitful, and foundational, especially for those envisaging conducting advanced academic research in future endeavors. I have listened to the video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck to supplement the coursepack and found it fruitful.

REFERENCES

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